

ROLL OF ANNABHAU SATHE IN SANYUKTA MAHARASHTRA MOVEMENT

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Maharashtra is one of the States of India which came in to existence on May 1st 1960 so, the day is celebrated every year as a birth anniversary. Sanyukta Maharashtra was a dream for every Maharashtrian and to fulfill this dream many had to accept imprisonment and 105 people sacrificed their life.¹ The present Maharashtra is the outcome of the creative and genius work of Senapati Bapat, S.M. Joshi, Acharya Atre, Comd. S.A. Dange, Bhai Uddhavrao Patil. Even Pandit Nehru opposed the movement of Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement but the agitations made by Marathi people unitedly with all their power & forgetting their political views and this chemistry resulted in success on May 1st 1960 awakening the self respect of Marathi people.²

Background:-

Annabhau Sathe is well known as a writer & Lokshahir Annabhau Sathe was born in Wategaon a village in Satara district. During the same period fight against British rule was in form in India and in Satara region Krantisingh Nana Patil's raised movement against Britishers. Annabhau Sathe was one of them hidden freedom fighters.³ Having this kind of revolutionary background he started his journey of life and later on he migrated to Mumbai for his daily bread with his family. When he was in Mumbai he came in to contact with labour movement & this contact resulted in making him a pure communist in his remaining life.⁴ With the help of this he contributed in the Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement awakening people with his Shahiri & Ballads. The Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement was its peak point and there was an atmosphere for separating Mumbai from rest of Maharashtra. In the year 1944 at Titwala in Farmers Conclave Annabhau Sathe with Amar Shaikh & Shahir Gavhankar established their Lal Bavta Kalapathak (Orechtra) in relation with IPTA (Indian Peoples Theater Association) and with Annabhau Sathe's participation and different features of his personality he was introduced to people of Maharashtra and this identity of Annabhau Sathe created a sparking & effective image of his own on the horizon of Sanyukta Maharashtra

Movement.⁵ Annabhau Sathe,Shahir Amar Shaik & Shahir Gavankar with the help of their Lal Bavta Kalapathak were boosting the movement & awaking people of Maharashtra.

Objective/Purpose of the research paper:-

To focus the contribution of Annabhau Sathe in Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement was the purpose of this research paper. Through he participated actively in this movement but his literary, culture & historical contribution to project his ideas in the boundries of communism remained in darkness.

Establishment of Sanyukta Maharashtra Committee:-

Sanyukta Maharashtra Committee was establish on 6th Feb.1956 under the leadership of Y.K.Sowani,G.T.Madkholkar,Comd.S.A.Dange,Acharya P.K.Atre,Madhu Dandwate,Bhai Uddhavrao Patil Prabodhankar K.C.Thakare at Pune.To form the state of Maharashtra with Mumbai (including) was the soul purpose of this Committee.⁶

Annabhau Sathe's work in Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement:-

Shahiri or Balled one of the forms of literature is always known for its awaking appeal,its spreading of consciousness and mass education.One can say it educates while entertaining.⁷ In Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement 'Maharashtrachi Parampara ' was the most famous Ballad by Annabhau sathe.⁸ He was not only a writer but he contributed in the 1942 movement against British rule. Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement and in freedom movement of Goa. He kept the flame of self respect burning among Indians with the help of his programmes. He sackles of slavery and tried his hand to awaken self confidance among the down trodens. Uniting people and educating them was an incomparable work done by Annabhau Sathe and is important historically and the historians has to take notice of this work.⁹

While working in Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement the duo,Annabhau Sathe and Amar Shaik ploughed the entire land of Maharashtra with their Shahiri and Powada's and the raised the common people on the side of Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement.¹⁰ Annabhau's shahiri revolted against the Government of Morarji Desai and S.K. Patil during the Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement and we may not offord forgetting the importance of his shahiri the way swords of the soldiers created history his shahiri too motivated maharashtrians to create history.¹¹ Annabhau Sathe is a well know shahir. Maharashtra is a state with rich tradition and this tradition reached to its clymax during Annabhau Sathe, shahir Gavankar and Amar Shaik's period. The shahiri written and performed by trio contributed a lot during Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement. It touched the hearts of Marathi peoples and made them rerady for revolution.The prayed the Goddess of freedom and sung Ballads of human freedom.¹²

They started the constructive work of awaking people and making them conscious about their well being. By one way the renaissance in India with the help of Lal Bavta Kalapathak.¹³ His Maharashtrachi Parampara, Mazi Mumbai, Mazi Maina Gavavar Rahili, Uthala Marathi Desh, Tu Marathmola & Sanyukta Maharashtra yet ase paha etc. Were the Lavnis on the lips of every Maharashtrian during Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement and it awakened the entire Maharashtra.¹⁴ Thus Annabhau Sathe's rebellions poetry and thoughts worked together to make people aware and together created the Sanyukta Maharashtra .Having a look on his work one can say that he was Maxim Gorky of Maharashtra.¹⁵ As he was a patriotic person,patriotism can be seen in his works of art. He gave importance to three things in his life viz.1) Unity of dalits, down trodans and farmers 2) Unification of Maharashtra with Konkan,Vidharbha,Marathwada,Belgaon and 3) National unity.¹⁶ Annabhau Sathe is today known as a revolutionary and reformer due to his literary and social contribution such as educating people,awakening them and paving the way in the world of literature.¹⁷ It was narrated with interest,how Annabhau Sathe with his fellow mets by breaking the Government rules and by playing the game of hide and seek with the police wandered throughout Maharashtra to pass the message with his shahiri and powada.¹⁸ He perform his shahiri before lakhs of peoples to inculeate among them that Mahararashtra should be modern,peaceful state of Marathi speaking people.It should be base on the equality principle Mahatma Phule,Chhat.Shahu Maharaj,Dr.B.R.Ambedkar.He wonder through out Maharashtra for the dream mentioned above. So it becomes mandatory to history of Maharashtra to make notice of him.¹⁹

Conclusion:-

Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement is a notable historical event in the history of Maharashtra. The state of Maharashtra with Mumbai as its capital come in to existence on May 1st 1960 as a result of State Reformation Commision, Dar Commision, Fazal Ali Commision, Satyagraha, Strikes, Martyrdom of 105 victims. In the creation of Sanyukta Maharashtra Annabhau Sathe's contribution is very much important. He Accepted the Marxist philosophy and with the help of his Lal Bavta Kalapathak reformed the life of workers,farmers and common people and made him participants in the movement.He work for communist party for most of his life but in the end the party neglected him forgetting everything and same is thing about his literary contribution.Even his crucial part in Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement is being forgottens by the historians and history as well. So the hidden star on the literary,cultural and historical horizon remained unknown for a longer time and it is the need of the hour to focus on it for justice.The state of Maharashtra is the out come of his honest work performed in

Sanyukta Maharashtra Movement.

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